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<p><i>Abstract</i></p> <p>This document gives a rough overview over the JURASSIC2 software, both its architecture and the intention of its individual components. In particular it notes the employed physical models and algorithms providing references to the literature describing them or on which the implementation was based. It is not a document allowing the reimplementation of the software and neither a document enabling its use otherwise unaided.</p> <p>It serves to give enough context and understanding towards being able to use the supplied examples in the SWB and make modifications to the employed scripts. To a lesser degree, it shall also give insight into the capabilities of the software beyond the use cases of the PerRec activity.</p>		
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1 Introduction

This document gives a rough overview over the JURASSIC2 software, both its architecture and the intention of its individual components. In particular it notes the employed physical models and algorithms providing references to the literature describing them or on which the implementation was based. It is not a document allowing the reimplementing of the software and neither a document enabling its use otherwise unaided.

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2 Background

Retrieving atmospheric quantities from limb sounder radiance measurements is a so called inverse problem. We can create a physics-based model that predicts measured radiances for a given atmospheric state, but there is no analytical function for the inverse. This is typically dealt with a minimization process, where the atmospheric state is modified in a smart fashion until the predicted radiances agree within reason with the measured radiances. The level 2 processing of CAIRT needs to solve a so called inverse problem. While it is rather straightforward to simulate measurements (using a so called forward model) given an atmospheric state, there is no easy way to do the reverse. In practice, one iteratively modifies the atmospheric state intelligently until the simulated measurements agree with the actual ones within reason.

Mathematically speaking, we have an atmospheric state $f \in L^2$ and a forward model $F: L^2 \mapsto \mathbb{R}^m$, which maps the atmospheric state f onto a discrete set of $m \in \mathbb{N}$ measurements. The forward model is of a physical nature and comparatively simple to compute. There is however no analytical or practical inverse to F . The inverse problem is then to identify the atmospheric state f , which fits to a given set of measurements y .

$$F(f) \stackrel{!}{=} y$$

This problem is often ill-posed such that, due to measurement noise in y or short-comings of F (which is only an approximation) no f exists that perfectly fits the measurements, or that noise in y has a determining influence on the result. As such, instead a minimization problem is solved:

$$\min_f \|F(f) - y\|_2^2,$$

where the Euclidean norm of the discrepancy between simulated measurements and actual measurements is minimized. The Euclidean norm chosen as it is the most fitting for the types of measurement errors normally encountered. Still, the influence of noise can be rather large, in particular if the measurements do not fully constraint the solution, which often necessitates the addition of an additional constraint $\Phi(f)$. Thus, the complete problem can be written as:

$$\min_f \left(\|F(f) - y\|_2^2 + \Phi(f) \right)$$

As practical necessity for a computer program, the function f will need to be represented by a discrete vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, on which the forward model F will operate. Also, the

measurement error in y will be taken into account by a random variable $\epsilon \in \mathbb{R}^m$ and a covariance matrix S_ϵ . This is combined to a cost function J , i.e.

$$\min_x J(x) = \min_x \left(\|S_\epsilon^{-1/2} (F(x) - y)\|_2^2 + \Phi(x) \right)$$

is the final problem to solve.

A good introduction into large-scale inversions (or retrievals) from a theoretical, practical, and algorithmic point of view has been given by the thesis of Ungermann (2011, chap. 2), which will thus not be repeated here. In fact, it assumes that this has been read before proceeding further in this document. For more recent developments, references are provided in the appropriate sections below.

This document provides a software-focused point of view detailing, how the algorithms are separated and implemented into individual software components.

The JURASSIC2 software package is a one-stop software solution that provides both a series of radiative transfer models for simulating measured radiances atmospheric states and a wide range of limb sounder instruments as well as a minimisation module that takes care of the iterative inversion process.

The data flow of a full inversion is shown in Figure 1.1 including all required input data. Another typical use case for JURASSIC2 is also the simulation of instruments to derive performance figures; it lacks a sophisticated instrument model, though, and is thus limited in its capabilities in that regard.

Figure 1: A general data flow chart of the basic elements of a retrieval. Data uses rounded boxes while processing happens in rectangles.

While JURASSIC2 supports all depicted steps, the core of JURASSIC2 deals with the iterative loop depicted on the right hand side.

3 JURASSIC2 software architecture

JURASSIC2 is a radiative transfer model that provides both radiances and derivative matrices (Jacobians) in combination with an efficient minimizer.

This document provides the general overview over the modules of the code and the most relevant/interesting features. Detailed descriptions of the involved algorithms are provided by the respective scientific publications which are referenced in the individual sections. Explicit implementation details (e.g. interfaces, data structures) are given in the software documentation supplied together with JURASSIC2.

JURASSIC2 is a fork of the C-based JURASSIC package. Both have been used by many published retrievals and studies (e.g. L. Hoffmann et al. 2008, 2009; Eckermann et al. 2009; L. Hoffmann and Alexander 2009; Weigel et al. 2010; Ungermann et al. 2010, 2020; Kalicinsky et al. 2013; Krisch et al. 2018; Höpfner et al. 2019; Bartolome Garcia et al. 2021; Krasauskas et al. 2021).

Figure 2: An overview of the architecture of the major components of JURASSIC2 and the control flow (i.e. which class/modules calls upon the functionality of what other ones). Mostly this is a "has a" relationship. E.g. The *CostFunction* "has a" *ForwardModel* and a *Covariance* member. The individual classes are described in respective sections below. In some cases, such as for the atmosphere, this is more complicated. It is "used" by the *Interpolation* in the context of the RTM, but it is actually contained in the *ForwardModel* to allow easier interfacing to the user.

The core of JURASSIC2 and most of the detailed functionality is implemented in C++ for performance reasons. The inner core of JURASSIC2 makes use of both OpenMP and MPI to achieve parallelization and employ more memory than is available on a single compute node. A typical use case on a high performance computer would be to employ both MPI and OpenMP parallelization. JURASSIC2 makes use of boost::python to expose almost all classes and functions of JURASSIC2 to python. Typically, python scripts perform all the interfacing and setting up of things before turning the number crunching over to the C++ core. All standard functionality is nowadays performed by python scripts.

A typical workflow looks as follows:

1. An *Atmosphere* is created. This class knows about the atmospheric state, i.e. which trace gases are represented and how the atmosphere is discretized.
2. A *ForwardModel* is created. This needs to know, radiances at which wavenumbers need to be computed, where the observers are located, and where they are looking. There are two levels involved.
 - *PencilBeams* are calculated by the model and are idealized 1-D radiative transfer computations.

- ‘SuperPixels’ are generated by summing over several PencilBeams with a set of weights to simulate, mostly, a point-spread-function.

For the simplest setups, there is a 1:1 relation between PencilBeams and SuperPixels.

3. Third, some ancillary quantities such as aerosol extinction and instrument parameters need to be configured. These allow rather elaborate features for advanced use, but can be typically neglected at first.

After this initial work, everything needed for forward computations is in memory. To enable retrievals, one needs to generate multiple ‘data sets’. Data sets offer the option to have multiple atmospheric states and radiances available to the model. A retrieval typically needs at least three data sets: one for measured radiances and a priori atmospheric state. One data set containing statistical uncertainties of measurements and atmospheric state. And a third data set to capture the retrieval result and the simulation radiances associated with said retrieved state. Additional data sets can be used for input or will be generated by the retrieval, e.g. for diagnostic results and error estimates if configured to do so.

After the model has been assembled in memory, one can continue working with it within the Python script. But in particular for automated large-scale processing, it is often useful to write the state to disk (there is a “write” method) and continue processing using the standard JURASSIC2 scripts. The most commonly used ones are

- jfm.py - for forward simulations
- jrp.py - for retrievals
- kernel.py - to compute Jacobian matrices

This allows more efficient use of HPC queuing systems, diagnosis and continuing of interrupted jobs. The scripts folder offers many examples of scripts setting up a simulation for a variety of purposes, often associated with different input (model) data. The most simple example for forward computations is “sim_himawari.py”, which simulates limb spectra of a geostationary satellite for all radiances for which tables are given in a supplied directory.

The generated NetCDF files are closely related to the internal data structures within JURASSIC2 and are thus not easy to interpret on their own. Thus, there is the create_ncdf.py script, whose primary purpose is to convert the internally used NetCDF file containing the result of a retrieval to a CF-compliant NetCDF file. If one desires the full information, it would be simplest to load the JURASSIC2 NetCDF file into memory by the “readSimply” function in pyjurassic.core and retrieve the necessary data using the “get” methods.

In the following, the major components of JURASSIC2, which typically correspond to C++ classes are discussed. JURASSIC2 uses a CamelCase naming scheme for classes, which provide the following section headings.

3.1 RadiativeTransferModel

JURASSIC2 implements several radiative transfer models. Some simple line-by-line and cross-section based accurate but slow models which are used for computing look-up-tables for the fast models. The main work horse for acceleration are band methods implementing the Curtis-

Godson-Approximation (CGA; (Curtis 1952; Godson 1953)) and Emissivity-Growth-Approximation (EGA; (Weinreb and Neuendorffer 1973; Gordley and Russell 1981)) to compute measured radiances. Both methods make use of precalculating the broadband emissions of homogeneous gas cells at various pressure/temperature/volume mixing ratios combinations and use some approximations to compute the emissions of an inhomogeneous ray path. Both were used successfully in the past in operational limb sounder retrievals, mostly for radiometer or filter like instruments. Their advantage is that the computational complexity does not increase with the number of lines affecting a radiance, but only the number of different emitters. The look-up tables contain already the convolution between the instrument line shape and an ideal spectrum.

Compared to conventional line-by-line calculations, the EGA and CGA approach is about a factor 1 000 faster, but loses some accuracy and has problems for instrument line shapes (ILS) with strong negative contributions (e.g. non-apodized FTS spectra). The accuracy of the method depends strongly on the examined wavenumber region and is very high in case of optically thin conditions. Comparisons between KOPRA (line-by-line) and JURASSIC have generally given an agreement better than 1%. That being sad, as the errors are often systematic they can be often be compensated with "offset" fitting terms in the retrieval. However, this is also part of the line-selection for the operational retrievals, where both the used lines and additional fitting parameters have to accommodate both the limitations of the available line data, the approximations of the model and the known and unknown uncertainties of the instrument at hand. Sabine Griessbach et al. (2013) did a comparison study and found the differences to be even below the MIPAS Envisat NESR levels for optically thin conditions and here examined wavenumber regions.

Please refer to Lars Hoffmann (2006) for a comprehensive discussion of the EGA method in the radiative transport model. The basic radiative transfer always works on an ideal Line-Of-Sight consisting of a series of homogeneous gas cells, which is computed from the position of the instrument to infinity. There is the option to combine EGA and CGA using a linear regression method (Francis et al. 2006) to improve accuracy, but while this method improves the accuracy of the simulated radiances, it does not seem to affect level 2 results in many circumstances. If performance is of essence, as it almost always is for tomographic retrievals, it is advantageous to only use the CGA method.

JURASSIC2 includes a basic line-by-line model that can provide the necessary look-up-tables (e.g. the included `gen_table.py` script), but it is recommended to use a more sophisticated programs such as the Reference Forward Model (RFM; (Dudhia, Morris, and Wells 2002)) or similar. The script contains a help and is very easy to use as generally only the wavenumber region, the spectral resolution of the instrument and the trace gas are to be specified. The generated table contains emissivities for homogeneous gas cells of a wide range of pressure/temperature/volume mixing ratios covering typical and atypical atmospheric conditions for the region where JURASSIC2 can reliably simulate radiances (i.e. in LTE conditions). A large set of precalculated tables is available, though, from the PerRec and CEEPS activities, such that a generation should not be necessary.

3.2 PencilBeam

The pencil beam is an idealisation of a "pencil-thin" beam of light passing through the atmosphere. Given a position in space (of the instrument) and a viewing direction, the PencilBeam

performs a sampling of the atmosphere along the line-of-sight. The line-of-sight includes typically refraction by the Earth atmosphere. Along the pencil beam a series of homogeneous gas cells is initiated to be supplied to the radiative transfer model. The sampling is typically adapted to the discretisation of the atmosphere and the desired accuracy of the computation.

3.3 Atmosphere

The atmosphere is typically a combination of geo-located points and associated atmospheric constituents such as temperature, pressure, or ozone volume mixing ratios. The atmosphere is designed to contain many separate *data sets* such as, e.g. the true value, the a priori value, or error estimates. The atmosphere itself is agnostic about its structure and is a simple "point cloud". Efficient interpolation requires knowledge about the spatial structure of the data, e.g., if the data is given on a rectilinear grid, multi-linear interpolation can be realized in a simple fashion. This knowledge about the structure is, however, not available to the atmosphere, but only known to the Interpolation classes discussed in the following. A configuration parameter determines, which constituents shall be treated in a logarithmic fashion for the retrieval which in particular effects the derivatives and the convergence behaviour of the retrieval.

3.4 Interpolation

Interpolation is the link from the atmospheric grid to the gas cells along the pencil beams. JURASSIC2 supports a variety of interpolation classes for different organisations of atmospheric data designed for different use cases. These typically expect a certain structure and/or order of points in the atmosphere to identify grids. The most basic interpolator assumes a 1-D atmosphere, but there are several different options for a variety of tomographic setups. These support both structured and unstructured data. While the unstructured data is more difficult to interpolate, one can achieve a sufficient representation with fewer points (e.g. by sampling with higher density in a region of interest). These are the included interpolators:

- 1-D linear interpolation
- 1-D linear interpolation with horizontal temperature gradient correction
- 2-D bilinear cross-section (see Ungermann (2013))
- 3-D trilinear satellite track interpolation (following a CAIRT like measurement track)

Further interpolation methods can be rather simply added as the architecture has been designed to be easily extensible. Each interpolator simply allows the extraction of atmospheric constituents at an arbitrary location based on provided Atmosphere data. Most of the interpolators extrapolate in a constant fashion beyond the provided data. One can also configure the model to take the logarithm of constituents before interpolation (and revert this for the result), which is best-practice for, e.g., extinction.

3.5 InstrumentModel

Figure 3: A simplified depiction of the instrument model.

The instrument model is the core of the model which ties the idealised computation of radiances on pencil beams together to simulated measurements. The instrument model contains a number of pencil beams sampling the field-of-view of one or several measurements by an instrument. Each actual measurement (called *superpixel* internally as it is assumed that several detector pixels have been binned, i.e. it is the opposite of a subpixel) is then a weighted average of the radiances of a subset of pencil beams, whereby the weights are typically provided by an spatial energy distribution function (SEDF) like function.

An *observation* is a radiance measurement at a given wavenumber on a given superpixel. This concept is very flexible and allows efficient simulation of many different instruments. Each pencilbeam may compute a different set of wavenumbers, one pencilbeam may be part of several superpixels (depending on the width and cut-off of the SEDF). For example, it is possible to simulate a spectrally varying SEDF by defining multiple, wavelength-dependent superpixels for one physical detector pixel for the respective spectral ranges. In this case, each superpixel uses a different set of weights for combining the radiance simulations along the pencilbeams. This is implemented by first computing all radiances for all pencilbeams and then combining to superpixels by using a sparse matrix-vector multiplication.

Figure 2.2 shows a simple example. Here, a set of pencilbeams are sent out from an observer position in a regular elevation grid of 0.01° distance. Here, two superpixels are shown as green and blue horizontal line including their SEDF. The weights can be computed from the crossings between the horizontal pencil beams and the SEDF function. To achieve higher precision, one should use a trapezoidal integral rule, in particular if one is forced to use fewer pencil beams to increase simulation speed.

In addition to this recombination, the instrument model also provides simple instrument effects of noise, offset, gain, or pointing changes, which can be assigned on a per-observation basis.

3.6 ForwardModel

The forward model (class) is a front-end combining the instrument model and the atmosphere. It realizes the realisation of the mathematical abstraction F introduced earlier. The class allows to

select an arbitrary subset of constituents stored in the atmosphere as vector x and provides a function mapping this x onto a set of function values y , i.e. the radiances. In effect, it works as a mathematical function F operating on vectors such as used in the description of retrieval in literature, e.g. by Rodgers (2000). In addition, it implements the computation of the Jacobian matrix F' of the forward model needed for the retrieval. The major method for computing the (sparse) Jacobian is an adjoint method (Ungermann et al. 2011), but finite differences are supported as well (both historically and for validation and testing; (Lars Hoffmann 2006)).

3.7 Covariance

The Covariance class implements the regularization both in a Thikonov sense and in an optimal estimation sense. The class typically builds an internal representation of the precision matrix, i.e. the inverse of the covariance matrix, which is either sparse or can be approximated by a sparse matrix. It is important to note that the class assumes a continuous perspective and approximates the integrals over the continuous atmospheric 1-D, 2-D, or 3-D field, e.g. by observing the trapezoid rule and taking distances between samples into account. It thus is largely grid independent, i.e., changing the atmospheric discretization should not change the result (unless, obviously, the implicit regularization due to a coarser gridding has a large impact). In particular for 1-D and 3-D atmosphere, the class allows for an auto-regressive optimal estimation approach (Tarantola 2004). Please refer to (Krasauskas et al. 2019) for an in-depth discussion. The result is in either case a sparse matrix L with $L^T L = S_a^{-1}$, with S_a^{-1} being the precision matrix.

3.8 CostFunction

The CostFunction class implements the mathematical function J introduced earlier and thus provides the missing mathematical abstraction to work with arbitrary minimizers. These can be also provided by python packages such as SciPy (Virtanen et al. 2020). In effect it combines the forward model with a regularization matrix and allows the evaluation of the cost function and its Jacobian and the product of the (approximated by neglecting the second derivative of the forward model) Hessian of the cost function with arbitrary vectors. In addition there are several convenience functions simplifying diagnostic computations, mostly associated with linear algebra operations on the involved matrices.

An important implementation detail of the cost function (and the minimizer described below) is full avoidance of any matrix-matrix multiplications by means of so-called functors. I.e. instead of computing the product of three matrices into a resulting matrix, an object storing the individual matrices and the operations is generated. When this "matrix" shall be multiplied with a vector later in the code, e.g. in the CG scheme, this can be evaluated step-by-step by multiplying the vector with each matrix in turn. This is significantly faster as the matrices are typically very sparse, whereas the total product would not be (Ungermann 2011, 222).

3.9 Minimizer

The architecture of the minimizer class allows for the implementation of different types of minimizers for the exploration of methods. Provided by open-jurassic2 is a Newton-type trust region method. The idea is to minimize the cost function provided by the cost function class using the Gauss-Newton method. To further stabilise the convergence, both Levenberg-Marquardt and general trust region methods are supplied. In particular for large scale problems, it is useful to

exploit the self-regularizing properties of the conjugate gradient scheme employed to solve the involved linear equation systems (LES) and thus save greatly in this step. The gist is to solve the initial LES only approximately (and thus quickly) and only tighten the convergence criteria in later steps of the conjugate gradient scheme (Steihaug 1983; Ungermann et al. 2010).

3.10 Diagnostics

The diagnostics module implements several different methods to compute linear Gaussian diagnostics as described by Rodgers (2000). The idea is to develop a Taylor approximation of first order around the solution to the minimization problem and use this to provide covariance matrices for a variety of error sources typically characterized as covariance matrices of perturbations of measured radiances.

The most straightforward method is the "dense" method, which uses simple matrix-matrix multiplications and inversions to compute the diagnostics as described by Rodgers (2000). Only for this method, the "functor" approach retaining the sparsity of involved matrices above needs to be necessarily discarded. It is to note that both matrix-matrix-multiplications and matrix-inversion are both computationally extremely costly and in the latter case also numerically unstable. Thus, this only works for small problems in the order of a few ten thousand unknowns.

Instead, one can use the "sparse" method to compute diagnostics for individual and configurable number of elements of the retrieval results. The diagnostics of each point require the solving of an LES, which is rather costly itself. The implementation allows for the solving of 8 points simultaneously, which should be considered when configuring the system by choosing always a multiple of 8. Computing the diagnostics for each set of 8 elements is similar costly as one (of typically 10-20) iteration steps of providing the full retrieval result. The results are numerically identical to the "dense" method.

Further, a Monte Carlo method has been implemented to provide diagnostics for all points. In contrast to the previous methods, this method does *not* compute the averaging kernel matrix and thus does not allow certain diagnostics of resolution and measurement contribution. Instead, it computes permutations of radiances according to the describing covariance matrices of uncertainties and uses these to compute both individual and total errors for the full retrieval vector. This uses linear retrievals, which, again, compute 8 solutions simultaneously. Astonishingly few solutions are required to provide solid estimates of errors. See Ungermann (2013) for a detailed discussion.

Last, the measurement contribution can be computed for all retrieved elements by solving a single LES, which is provided by a separate method.

3.11 ControlStruct

The configuration of JURASSIC2 is realized by a python file, which sets global variables, which are parsed by a C++ class. Most parameters are transferred to a C++ representations such that they can also be accessed in high-performance parallel sections, but some remain stored solely in the underlying Python dictionary and are accessed via Python in non-performance critical code. All parameters are documented in the code and extracted and collected in the documentation.

3.12 Adjoined

JURASSIC2 makes use of its own library for operator overloading to tape the execution of the forward model and roll the tape back to compute the adjointed model, which allows the direct computation of one row of the Jacobian matrix. For details of the technique and its application to JURASSIC2, please refer to Giering and Kaminski (1998), (Leppkes and Naumann 2011), (Lotz, Naumann, and Ungermann 2011), and (Ungermann 2011). We apply the adjointed method individual radiances of the pencil beam. The cost to compute the Jacobian in this fashion can be as low as 2 to 5 times the cost of the execution of the model itself, whereby a factor of 5 can often be achieved in practice (e.g. Griewank and Walther 2008, 83ff). This makes this approach much more efficient for large vectors and tomographic applications, where the number of atmospheric constituents go in the millions.

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